

Unveiling the relation between aortic shape and calcification in population with aortic stenosis: Towards better management of TAVI patients

Raphael Sivera¹, Ebba Montgomery-Liljeroth¹, Andrew Cook¹, Silvia Schievano¹, Kush Patel², Claudio Capelli¹

¹Institute of Cardiovascular Science, University College London, London, UK; ²Bart's Heart Centre, St Bartholomew's Hospital, London, UK

Introduction: Transcatheter aortic valve implantation (TAVI) is a well-established and minimally invasive procedure to treat patients with aortic stenosis (AS). It is a therapeutic option for an increasing number of patients but its complications, such as mild paravalvular regurgitation, may still have a undesirable impact on the long-term outcome. Aortic valve calcification evaluation and modelling can be crucial to understand evolution of AS, improve TAVI outcomes or develop non-surgical treatments [1,2]. This work aims to unveil the relation between the aortic root shape and calcification in the AS population. **Method:** Clinical data were retrospectively collected from a population (n=130) that underwent TAVI at our clinical centre. Large-deformation atlas modelling [3] based on CT images was used to characterize the aortic shape variability and to standardize the position of the 3D segmented calcified areas. The calcification patterns were then projected on 2D surfaces corresponding to the valve and the ascending aorta. Sparse principal component analysis (sPCA) was performed to represent the calcifications using a limited set of spatially localized atoms. Finally, cross-decomposition using partial least squares (PLS) was computed to analyse the relationship between shape and the calcification patterns. Bootstrapping was performed to assess the stability of the results. **Results:** PLS highlighted up to 3 modes of correlation between shape and calcification. First, small and narrow aortas were associated with less calcification with the stronger effect localized on both the right and left coronary cusps (RCC and LCC). The second mode suggested that rounder and short lobes could be associated with less calcification on the RCC-LCC junction. The third mode linked the tilt of the aorta and the average calcification of the valve. **Conclusion:** This work provides new evidence of important morphological properties affecting the pathological processes leading to aortic valve calcification. This can be used to simulate synthetic data for the assessment of personalized TAVI planning strategies.

References:

1. Bogdanova et al. 2022.
2. Shi et al. 2023.
3. Durrleman et al. 2014.